

FEATURES OF MENTAL DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract: The essence of the article is that every person in the world experiences the period of preschool age in the process of development. At this time, the child's worldview expands, he begins to understand the difference between good and bad, and begins to engage in interpersonal communication. At this age, more attention should be paid to the education of the child.

Key words: Mental development, game, leading activity, communication, cognitive processes, crisis.

In ontogeny, in personal development, the period from three to seven years is the kindergarten or preschool age period. One of the prominent characteristics of children at this age is their mobility and imitability. That is, almost most of them are riotous, more playful and imitate cartoon or fantasy movie characters. They feel like the same hero. At this point, it should be said that the leading activity of preschool children is play.

According to the famous Russian pedagogue Legsgaft, the period of kindergarten age is such a stage, during which children's character traits are formed and the foundations of moral character are formed.

Through relationships with adults and peers, he begins to recognize moral standards, understanding people, and positive and negative relationships. At this time, in addition to family education, the child receives education from the environment, i.e., through communication and relationship culture with other alien adults and peers. New relations between children and adults, the image of an adult directs the child's behavior in a certain direction, which serves as a basis for the emergence of all new psychological structures in the development of the child's personality. During this period, the child's speech begins to develop rapidly, he seeks to consolidate what he knows in relation to acquiring news. It is also worth mentioning that he listens to the tales he knows over and over again and does not get bored of them. Such situations are characteristic of children of this period. Children of preschool age become more interested in all events and phenomena in the environment. That is, children at this age become inquisitive due to increased interest. And through this they get more information. The importance of interest in a child's growth and development is that the child seeks to know what he is interested in deeply enough and does not

get bored of doing what he is interested in for a long time. Almost most children at this age are Erka, a do-it-yourself freak.

It is known that as the age of the child grows and the possibility of independent action increases, his worldview of things and sensations around him expands. The leading activity of preschool children is play. Games of children of this age can be divided into 3. These are: 1. Object games. It will be played for 15-20 minutes. 2. Story-role games. It is played for 30-60 minutes. 3. Regular games. It can last from 1 hour to 2 days. The question of play activities of children of kindergarten age has attracted the attention of many scientists for centuries. Kindergarten children strive to reflect in their play activities all aspects of our rich and moving life.

It should be mentioned that the game is not only a means of learning about the events in the environment, but also a powerful means of education. It is necessary to be more careful when telling them a story. It is permissible for a fairy tale to end well. If it doesn't end well, it can have a negative effect on them.

By giving proper education to three-year-old children, influencing them, and directing their actions in accordance with the purpose, it is possible to achieve the formation of the skills of independent eating, dressing, washing, tidying up, and the ability to perform some tasks and tasks carefully. The psychological characteristics of three-year-old children are that achieving physical independence creates a desire in the child to be free, without the supervision of adults, to do some work on his own, to live as an individual in the environment in general. The period up to the age of three is the stage of the most reasonable manifestation of speech and speech activity and the correct, appropriate development. It depends on the adult that the child pronounces the words fluently and completely. When the child is 3 years old, the concept of "I" begins to form. That is, concepts such as this toy is mine, this dress is mine, and this bag are mine begin to appear. A child's age of 3 can be called the age of stubbornness. Obstinacy to petting is also common in 3-year-olds. Giving a child more love than usual, pampering him too much, making him do whatever he wants, unconditionally fulfilling his demands and needs also creates masculinity and stubbornness in him. Praising the behavior of the child, what he has done, teasing him inappropriately, or treating him with indifference also causes stubbornness. Ignoring the child, not controlling, not checking also leads to bad situations. For example, neglect hurts a child, makes him feel lonely and hopeless. In such a case, it causes internal conflict, mutual conflict and conflicts in the child in relation to adults. A child who is stubborn should not be

pampered, praised, or fulfill all his wishes. Paying equal attention to everyone, whether in the family or in kindergarten, and not leaving the child alone will help prevent stubbornness. A three-year-old child does not know how to behave in a public place, among many people. That's why it should be explained by adults. In the formation of the personality of three-year-olds, it is very important to teach them to finish what they have started, to overcome difficulties, to be patient, to be patient, to restrain themselves, and not to act excessively. The moral example of adults is of particular importance in the formation of a child as a person. That is, don't do this, do this, this is wrong, this is right, this is good, this is bad, and they are warnings.

Among the creative activities of young children of this period, they especially like painting. Depending on what and how the child expresses it, one can think about the uniqueness of his perception of events in the world, his memory, imagination and thinking. Through pictures, children try to convey their thoughts and knowledge from the outside world. Pictures can change depending on the child's psychological and physical condition. The pictures drawn by sick children are completely different from the pictures drawn by healthy children. For example, when we say to a young child to draw your parents and yourself, when we hold hands and draw them, the family atmosphere, education, attitude and communication will be good. On the contrary, if he does not hold hands together or draw hands, his family environment, upbringing, attitude and communication will not be good. Taking into account that there are very rapid quality changes in the psychology of preschool children, it is divided into 3 periods: 1.3-4-year-old preschool period, i.e. kindergarten age; 2.4-5 years of pre-secondary school period, i.e. middle kindergarten age; 3.6-7 years old can be divided into pre-school period, i.e. senior kindergarten age. Basically, from this period, the independent activity of the child begins to increase and self-confidence begins to increase.

Children of kindergarten age develop intuition, perception, attention, memory, imagination, thinking, speech, imagination, emotions and will. The child cannot distinguish colors well yet. It is necessary to give him toys, colored rings, boxes and other types of toys that help him learn the difference of colors. Only then will they begin to distinguish color clearly. Kindergarten children's attention spans are largely involuntary. Play is very important for the development of voluntary attention in children of kindergarten age.

Children of senior preschool age can now move independently. They wash and dress themselves. But all the same, they try to be pampered by their parents.

Parents use the following methods of child education: 1. Authoritarian style-management is conducted on the basis of strictness. Initiative in a child is forbidden by parents. Any behavior will be punished. Children brought up by this method become timid, fearless, unable to realize their potential. Because parents do not create conditions for them. 2. Liberal method - in this method, the parent is indifferent to his child, he is not interested in what he is interested in, what he has. A child does not understand what is bad and what is good. As a result, children cannot act independently and actively. 3. The democratic method is a productive method of education, in which parents give their child all their love and consider his interests and possibilities. He wants the child to think freely. This method makes it possible to properly raise a child.

In some families, there may be an only child, too much caressing them, by doing what they say, leads to the formation of a selfish person, that is, a person who only thinks about himself. Or an older child starts to resent his parents and grandparents from his brother or sister who was born after him. Because at that time, the relatives of the child pay more attention to the baby who arrived in the New World. In such a situation, if adults explain correctly that you can now do independent work, you can satisfy your needs in a certain way, the child will be kind to his brothers and sisters. It is permissible not to belittle a child of preschool age and not to be extremely rude and harsh to him. If such an attitude is expressed, the child will become a coward, unable to express his opinion in the future. He will not be able to freely express his opinion in the public place or in the family circle. It should also be noted that if parents tell their child that others are good and you are bad, that he is smart and polite and you are not, then the child's confidence in his son will decrease, that means he will have negative thoughts that he is not a good, smart and polite child. possible

Preschool children are better taken by kindergarten. Because a group of children is formed in kindergarten. By exchanging ideas and communicating with each other, the child begins to develop a deeper understanding of the external world, broadening of his worldview, and receptiveness.

At the age of preschool education, the ability to deal with the situation also improves. A child of this age will understand the meaning of words such as "now", "before", "before" and "arrive late", "arrive on time", "stay long", "be fast". So, children of this age have an idea and some concepts about time. Children's play activities greatly help them to develop a sense of time. During the game, one has to always pay attention to one's actions and the actions of the partners participating in the game, take into account the speed and intensity of the

actions, and wait for the result of the game, that is, the action. Also, it is necessary for children to pay attention to slowness, agility or slowness of movement even when working according to their strength. Often, adults also demand that the child do some work quickly and quickly. Children try to speed up their movements in order to obey the commands of adults to "hurry up". Children themselves also try to "rush" to do something "faster". A strict regime established in kindergarten and family helps to develop a sense of time in children. Every day, children should sleep in the same place, eat food, do some work or play, etc. Six- to seven-year-old children start time by looking at the clock.

The famous Russian psychologist L.S. Vygotsky called the crisis of this age the seven-year crisis and pointed out the changes in the child's behavior and character. The childish immediacy disappears in the child's behavior. Symptoms of a crisis include grimacing, pretending, and clowning, which serve to protect against traumatic experiences.

Currently, in our country, preschool children are taught mental arithmetic, reading, writing and counting in kindergarten. Children go to school with partial knowledge of reading, writing, counting and arithmetic. The importance of mental arithmetic is that children perform calculations, that is, mathematical operations through imagination, imagination and thinking. Another feature is that they work orally without writing down mathematical operations. For information, it should be said that there are also competitions among children who know mental arithmetic.

Preschool age is an intensive stage of mental development. It is from this age that the child undergoes great changes, that is, the processes that take place from the improvement of psychophysiological functions to the emergence of complex new personal images. Analyzing new images and imaginary events is characteristic of children of preschool age, but even if the results are not always positive, when we analyzed children's activities, we were sure that children not only imagine objects, but also imagine their interrelationships. The development of imagination is characterized by the process of formation of thinking, this formation is related to the voluntary indicators of the child's imagination. Such a possibility is even higher in 5-6-year-old children, because the child's behavior is important in the process of education and upbringing, in which the child acquires new mental movement methods very quickly. This, in turn, is the period of optimal opportunity for the development of imaginative thinking of children of preschool age.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. M.Maxsudova. "Muloqot psixologiyasi". Toshkent "Turon-iqbol" 2006-yil.
2. P.I.Ivanov; M.E.Zufarova. "Umumiy psixologiya". O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti Toshkent 2008-yil.
3. Z.Nishanova, Z.Qurbonova, S.Abdiev. "Psixodiagnostika va eksperimental psixologiya". "Tafakkur-Bo'stoni". Toshkent 2011-yil.
4. Egamberdiyev J. SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF ORGANIZING SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 209-214.
5. Egamberdiyev J. THE ROLE OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES IN FORMING THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF YOUTH //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 110-117.
6. Egamberdiyev J. THE INFLUENCE OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES ON THE SPIRITUALITY OF YOUTHS IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION //Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA». – 2024. – №. February 23 2024; Amsterdam, Netherlands. – С. 216-220.
7. Egamberdiyev J. THE ROLE OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES IN FORMING THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF YOUTH //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 110-117.
8. Хуррамов М. Г. и др. Энергосберегающее устройство для выделения волокнистых и грубодисперсных примесей из технологических стоков красильно-отделочного производства //Известия высших учебных заведений. Технология текстильной промышленности. – 2021. – №. 3. – С. 132-135
9. Хуррамова Н. М. и др. Перспективные направления переработки осадков стоков для получения почвоулучшающей композиции в сельском хозяйстве //Вестник Белорусской государственной сельскохозяйственной академии. – 2023. – №. 1. – С. 187-190.
10. Хуррамова Д. М. ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОЕ ПОЛЕ" ОЧИСТКА СТОЧНЫХ ВОД" //Вестник магистратуры. – 2023. – №. 3-2 (138). – С. 78-80.
11. Хуррамов М. Г. и др. Способ доочистки технологические стоков красильно-отделочного производства //Энергосбережение и водоподготовка. – 2019. – №. 2. – С. 21-24
12. Jabborov, Jamshid. "ANALYSIS OF NEEDS IN THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF WESTERN SCIENTISTS." Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA» February 9, 2024; Athens, Greece (2024): 94-98.

13. Azimovich, Jabborov Jamshid. "MA'NAVIY EHTIYOJLAR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-MADANIY OMILLARI." Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences 1.3 (2021): 30-35.
14. Жабборов, Ж.А. (2021). Интерпретация проблемы духовных потребностей в научных исследованиях ученых нашей страны. Общество и инновации, 2(5/S), 484–491. <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss5/S-pp484-491>
15. Жабборов, А. М., Жабборов, И. А., & Жабборов, Ж. А. (2015). ЭТНИЧЕСКИЕ СТЕРЕОТИПЫ И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ САМОБЫТНОСТИ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (1), 80-83.
16. Жабборов, А. М., & Жабборов, Ж. А. (2016). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УЗБЕКСКИХ НАРОДНЫХ ПОСЛОВИЦ ПРИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ УЧЕБНО-ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (3), 93-95.
17. Жабборов Ж.А. Маънавий эҳтиёжлар – жамият тараққиётининг мезони // «Трансформація суспільних наук: соціально-економічний, лінгвістичний, політичний та іт-виміри» II Міжнародна наукова конференція. 22.10.2021. Харків, UKR. 40-43 бет. <https://doi.org/10.36074/mcnd-22.10.2021>

